

LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS OF
LEXICAL UNITS EXPRESSING THE CONCEPT OF "HAPPINESS" AND
"UNHAPPINESS" IN ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11212795>

Abstract. In this article shows the national-cultural characteristics of phraseological expressions related to the concepts of "Happiness" and "Unhappiness" in English and the translation of these phraseological units into Uzbek.

Key words: linguistics and culture, concept, phraseological unit, paremiology.

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ
ЕДИНИЦ, ВЫРАЖАЮЩИХ ПОНЯТИЕ «СЧАСТЬЕ» И «НЕСЧАСТЬЕ» В
АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье показаны национально-культурные особенности фразеологизмов, связанных с понятиями «Счастье» и «Несчастье» в английском языке и перевод этих фразеологизмов на узбекский язык.

Ключевые слова: языкознание и культурология, концепт, фразеологизм, паремиология.

In the English and Uzbek languages, the lexemes "happiness" and "bakht" are one of the concepts that express human feelings. Although the lexeme of happiness as a separate concept means specific feelings of trust, it is also connected with feelings of love and friendship. In English and Uzbek languages, in many cases, achieving love is connected to the concept of happiness.

After all, achieving love also represents the concept of achieving the content of a happy life. In fiction, the duality of happiness and unhappiness between people is connected with the kindness of the tole. This duality can be not only the object of influence of higher powers, but also the object of good deeds that show their will and ability to influence people. Happiness is a specific feeling, that is, it expresses the concept of achieving the content of a happy life, and there are also features of not achieving such happiness, which brings out the concept of the dyad of unhappiness. Happiness coexists with unhappiness.

Happiness is achieved gradually, and unhappiness comes with flapping wings.

Unhappiness means bad luck. Lexical explanations and competent definitional analysis show that happiness is called "happiness" in English, and the meaning of "bad luck" is associated with different fields. Concepts such as happiness and poverty in human life appear through them.

There are different forms of lexemes that reflect this relationship. They are represented by the lexeme "Unhappiness" to one core, that is, the concept of "happiness". Failure is an accident.

It shows unexpected disappointments. Therefore, it is possible to consider the concepts of happiness and unhappiness as independent concepts. We know that every person strives to live a happy life and avoid unhappiness throughout his life. As a person's knowledge and life experience increases, his ideas about happiness change and take shape. If we pay attention to the history of mankind, it can be observed that people's thoughts, ideas and imaginations about this notion or concept are connected with consistency.

The thinkers of the past have proven in their works that the concept of "happiness" is manifested in different situations and emphasized that it is one of the highest feelings of a person in social life. In this regard, a lot of stories and narrations, wisdom and proverbs - paremias have been created in the national language.

The concept of "happiness" is understood differently by everyone. For example, one of the wise men wrote about happiness, bliss and life in a letter to his son: "Dear son, listen carefully to my words. Don't take a place among those who struggle because they are not lucky, if you work hard, you will be lucky. Perhaps some of your work may not turn out as successful as you wish, but don't worry about it and despair. Don't lose your enthusiasm and courage. From what seems to be difficult and difficult, in reality, many important and good results can be obtained. Don't get too carried away by trivial things and material decorations.

Strive to become the possessor of grace and perfection. Learn from the lives of great people in history. Be gentle, kind, and gracious. All these are the foundations of happiness." Socrates says: "A person who is satisfied with a little thing is a statesman, because such satisfaction indicates his spiritual wealth. There is nothing in the world that a person can't overcome, so don't be afraid, use your energy and enthusiasm and move forward. Do not think that happiness and bliss will fall from the sky or appear out of nowhere. If you think like this, you will be considered one of the most ignorant people in the world" [2]. Happiness does not consist only of material world, career or fleeting feelings. Every blessing of God is happiness.

The master of two worlds Muhammad Mustafa (pbuh) said: "Whoever wakes up in the morning with his house safe, his body healthy, and his daily food, it is as if the whole world is gathered around him."

When analyzing words and phrases expressing the concepts of happiness and unhappiness in English, first of all, we need to have a comprehensive understanding of foreign language words and their scope of use. Because, as in Uzbek, in English, each word has its own meaning and places of use.

There are many words and phrases representing the happiness segment in all languages. In addition, the English language that we are considering now has several objects that express the concept of happiness.

Happiness is one of the most popular and multifaceted topics in everyday life and in science. use is no less than others. There are many words and idioms, proverbs and expressions that mean happiness in the English language, and their diversity in thought and form attracts the attention of scientists and everyone interested in this topic, as well as the author.

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